

Speculation on Quantum Spatial Distributions in $\exp(ipx)$ and Inertia

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We have argued in previous notes that the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ represents two spatial distributions in two dimensions (i.e. at different times). We have further argued that a spatial distribution is linked to p , the impulse, needed to create the momentum in the first place. Thus a free particle contains a kind of stored impulse/force manifested by the distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. Two dimensions are needed to give the semblance of smooth motion i.e. $x=p/m t$ on average.

In (1) we argued that the even in the case of a Newtonian impulse $\int F dt$ which one might assume occurs at a point x (as in two body collisions in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas), there must be a dx range as the energy $pp/2m$ follows from $\int F dx$ which requires such a dx . In Newtonian mechanics everything is smooth, so there is constant acceleration within dx , but we argue that such a smooth picture violates the idea of action-reaction and inertia. Thus we argue that Newtonian mechanics should lead to the notion of an x -distribution within dx even if the particle is a point. This x -distribution which exists as the particle is under force does not disappear when the external force is removed because a particle with momentum p represents an impulse (which in turn includes a force). With the external force removed, one might expect there is nothing to maintain an x -distribution i.e. action/reaction has stopped. In one sense this is true as the particle moves through space as if each x point carries the same weight. On the other hand, the Newtonian idea of inertia, even with no momentum suggests one does not simply have a translating object. The idea of inertia i.e. rest mass should be linked then to the spatial distribution associated with the wavelength \hbar/p which we argue happens in special relativity.

The Notion of dx and dt

Velocity is defined as dx/dt so it seems that in Newtonian mechanics the notion of dx and dt must exist. It must also exist, even, if on average, in quantum mechanics because a quantum free particle such as an electron (or a photon) has a speed which may be measured. In (1) we noted that a Newtonian impulse $\int F dt$ integrates out time. A particle with 0 momentum might receive an impulse and change to p , but its energy is then $pp/2m$. This energy, however, follows from $\int F dx$ and so there must be an dx in the picture even for an impulse.

In Newtonian mechanics everything is smooth, so even if there exists a dx , to first order a constant acceleration acts on the particle which has a constant velocity to leading order as dx is tiny. The problem with this scenario, we argue, is that it seems to contradict Newtonian mechanics, namely the idea of action-reaction and even inertia. We argue that a particle under an external force exhibits a reaction which should be noticeable in x space as the force is trying to move the particle in x . In particular, we suggest that an x -distribution should be visible within dx . Newtonian mechanics does allow for a "density" change from one dx to another through different dt values ($dx=\text{constant}$) i.e. it is sometimes said that the classical density of a Newtonian particle is:

density(x) of a Newtonian particle = $C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ =velocity ((1))

This, however, is a constant density within dx which suddenly changes when one moves from x to $x+dx$, just as $v(x)$ suddenly changes. One does not get the sense of an action-reaction within dx as the particle is interacting, but Newton's third law states that such an action-reaction exists.

Thus we suggest an x distribution within dx indicating that the particle is under the action of a force. Given that $\text{Force} = -dV/dx$ and that a higher p means a higher impulse, one might consider the distribution to be sharper for a higher p . Such a picture might be fine while the particle is interacting with an external force, but what happens when the particle reaches its final p value and the external force is removed? One might expect no action reaction any longer, but a momentum p does not simply represent a constant velocity, it represents an impulse which may be delivered at any moment. Thus we do not think it is unreasonable that an x - distribution still exists even for a constantly moving object. This, however, leads to a major issue because the point particle is supposed to move deterministically as $x=p/m t$.

The Notion of Probability

While a particle interacts with an external force, one might argue that unusual things may happen as action-reaction occurs. Once the external force is removed, the particle simply moves with a constant velocity in Newtonian mechanics. This velocity may be measured experimentally. The particle, however, represents an impulse/momentum and this force should be manifested, possibly through a spatial distribution as we have argued in previous notes. Thus there are two problems:

- (A) The presence of an x distribution suggesting a force should also suggest an action-reaction.
- (B) On average the particle must move smoothly according to $x=p/m t$ which is at odds with an x distribution.

Given the notion of $x=p/m t$, a spatial distribution has the appearance of a probability distribution in x . The particle, however, is moving as seen by an external ruler and clock and so it is not clear if different points in a region dx are associated with the distribution or with motion. Furthermore, if there is motion, there should be an x -distribution associated with the new x point. Thus one has two distributions within the same dx region. Translational motion, however, is real and so one might think of the two distributions being represented by a pair i.e.

$$(x\text{-distribution}_1(px), x\text{-distribution}_2(px)) = (P_1(px), P_2(px)) \quad ((2))$$

An interesting feature is that their x ranges of $P_1(px)$ and $P_2(px)$ overlap in space. We have written px as the argument because we noted above that a sharp derivative indicates a large force and a large p should do the same. Thus we expect a slope sharpness proportional to p .

One may next ask whether ((2)) with p is the same as ((2)) with $-p$? If so, one could not distinguish the direction of motion. Thus we assume that one distribution is even in p and the other odd. We take $P_1(px)$ to be even and $P_2(px)$ to be odd.

Given the average relationship $x = p/m t$ each x point is associated with one time point t . Each x point, however, has the same “weight” i.e. dt is the same for each dx because of the constant speed. ((2)) is associated with two distributions, thus there is a $P_1(px)$ and $P_2(px)$ at each x . One might try to argue that if one is at x it means that the particle has not translated and is at x due to distribution P_1 or that it has translated and is at x due to distribution $P_2(px)$. This would lead to the notion of:

$$P_1(px) + P_2(px) = 1 \quad ((3))$$

((3)), however, violates the idea that $P_1(px)$ is even and say $P_2(px)$ is odd. It would mean that $P_1(-px) + P_2(-px) = 1$, but this means that $P_1(px) - P_2(x) = 1$ or $P_1(px) = 1$ and there is no distribution in x as in Newtonian mechanics.

Thus as argued in (2), one must try to freeze out the motion in ((2)) in order to see the equal x weights implied by $x = p/m t$ because these equal weights hold whether one uses p or $-p$. Thus one has:

$$\text{Probability pair } (p) * (\text{AND}) \text{ Probability pair } (-p) = \text{constant} \quad ((4))$$

The two probability distributions appear to be “orthogonal” after the failure of ((3)). Thus:

$$P_1(px)P_1(px) + P_2(px)P_2(px) = \text{constant} \quad ((5))$$

Assuming $P_1(px)$ and $P_2(px)$ are periodic (which introduces a kind of spatial invariance) then:

$P_1(px) = \cos(px)$ and $P_2(px) = \sin(px)$ is a solution of ((5)) or one has $\exp(ipx)$ for a free quantum particle.

Thus because there is motion in a certain direction and $P_2(px)$ must carry this information, while $P_1(px)$ does not, one has $P_1(px)$ and $P_2(px)$ treated as orthogonal. We will argue later that a similar feature exists for rest mass m_0 and p in $E = pc + m_0c^2$ ($c=1$). Both p and m_0 represent “forces” in the sense that p is associated with an impulse and m_0 with inertia, but p may have either a positive or negative sign, while m_0 must be positive for matter. Thus there is again an orthogonality due to completely separate information.

By having two x -distributions $P_1(x)$ and $P_2(x)$ treated as orthogonal, one may “combine” the two in order to create the semblance of all x points having the same weight. One may also consider the two distributions to represent action -reaction against each other. The force associated with the impulse p is stored in both $P_1(px)$ and $P_2(px)$, but they act-react against each other. A negative portion of $P_1(px)$ is fine as it is the combination $\exp(ipx)$ which is important. We argue, however, that the presence of negative values of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ indicates action-reaction.

The Notion of Inertia

We argued that in Newtonian mechanics a particle at rest seems to offer resistance to an external force simply because it has a rest mass i.e. inertia. When the particle moves, it has a momentum which represents an impulse or force. This is interesting because a rest mass is linked with inertia, which is like a “force” and so is associated with momentum, but rest mass is also energy and associated with overall energy in special relativistic transformations. Even though rest mass transforms in the place of energy in a 4-vector, momentum is still $m_0 v/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ so modified rest mass is part of the momentum and it is the full momentum which represents an impulse/force.

Thus we argue that the idea of an internal force in x seems to be associated with the notion of matter and it seems that the notion of a point (e.g the center-of-mass point) does not capture this idea. There should be some x -distributions present.

We note, as we have pointed out before, that the notion of a frequency and wavelength i.e. time and x probability distributions follow from the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad (6)$$

with time period = \hbar/E and wavelength = \hbar/p . Thus special relativity introduces special time and space intervals linked with p . Furthermore, $\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar d/dx$ where $dA/dx = p$.

Finally we note that in the case of the two distributions $P_1(px) = \cos(px)$ and $P_2(px) = \sin(px)$, the first is even and the second is odd to indicate motion. Thus one cannot add $P_1(px)$ and $P_2(px)$. They exist “in different orthogonal dimensions” so to speak in terms of information.

The same seems to be true with rest mass and p which both represent force. In this case p may be positive or negative. Thus $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 c^2$ ($c=1$). Even though this equation follows from the Lorentz invariant dot product: (E,p) dot with metric $(1,-1)$ with $(E,p) = (m_0, 0)$ dot with metric $(1,-1)$ $(m_0,0)$, the form $p^2 + m_0^2$ suggests one is adding two identical physical entities. If one thinks of p as impulse/force and m_0 as inertia, then both have the sense of force, but p may be $-p$ or p so from an information point of view (motion in the positive or negative direction) it is orthogonal to m_0 .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that the x -probability distributions in $\exp(ipx)$ seem to follow from notions in Newtonian mechanics, namely inertia and action-reaction. We argue that action-reaction should be manifest spatially within dx as a particle and an external force act-react. Instead, in Newtonian mechanics the spatial difference is seen in one dx and its adjacent dx through the spatial density $C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity. We argue for an x -distribution within dx . This leads to problems if the external force is removed, but even a particle with constant p represents an impulse/force. Thus we argue for retaining the probability distribution, but combining it with a second one associated with translation i.e. $P_1(px)$ and $P_2(px)$. We use px because we think the sharpness of the distribution should be proportional to

the impulse as in $F=-dV/dx$. We further argue that $P1(px)$ and $P2(px)$ should indicate direction of motion so one is even in p and the other odd. Thus if one tries to write $P1(px)+P2(px)=1$ one encounters problems because given $P1(px)$, $P2(px)$ are orthogonal in information because $P1(px)$ does not know the direction of motion i.e. is even. Thus we combine $P1(px),P2(px)$ as orthogonal pieces i.e. create the inner product: $P1(px)P1(px)+P2(px)P2(px) = \text{constant}$ to indicate that all p points have the same weight. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a solution.

We further link the notion of internal force to the idea of rest mass. We note that both rest mass/inertia and p represent forces, but again for a given rest mass, one cannot possibly know if p is p or $-p$ so we suggest the picture $momo + pp$ which in fact is part of the Lorentz invariant: $EE= pp + momo$ ($c=1$). We also point out again that the notion of wavelength = \hbar/p and $\exp(ipx)$ follow from the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$.

References

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- 2.
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